

SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF CREATIVITY IN THE ACTIVITY OF AN ENTREPRENEUR

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Annotation The article deals with issues such as the formation of rationality, thrift, entrepreneurship, business acumen, innovation, foresight, development of professional skills and competences of entrepreneurs, and the social importance of creativity.

Key words: market relations, economic activation, rationality, thrift, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurship, innovation, predictability, intellectual qualities, creativity.

We can consider it as a catalyst for the transformation of our society through the formation of a digitized economy, a social people-friendly state, a free society in which the elements of market relations are embodied, through the social and economic activation of citizens, the manifestation of the individual's intellectual potential, and the development of positive qualities. Therefore, forming the qualities of our population, especially the youth, such as rationality, frugality, entrepreneurship, business acumen, innovation, and the ability to predict is one of the urgent tasks. As a result, it is of great importance for the development of our country to get rid of getting used to saying "okay" to everything, giving in to excessive indifference, and on the contrary, raising our future generation with active, intellectual qualities.

It should be noted that "according to the goals and ideals of each new society, the worldview and understanding of the world of the new generation is formed, the settlement and development of the new society, in turn, requires the spirit of spiritually renewed, developed and formed generations. The new society first ripens in the nation's dream and heart, after it becomes an objective reality (of course, there are many ways to turn it into an objective reality), it settles in the form of a social organism representing the way of life and development of the general public, the people raised by the same society, the advanced worldview and thinking of the general public. will be necessary. The development of society depends on high national consciousness, and high national consciousness depends on fair humanization of society. The commonality of these social factors, which require each other and determine each other's development, are the forces that guarantee the national interests and prospects of the society and the country" [1].

Just as economic activity is important in the lives of young people, so is ideological education and its inculcation. Based on this - "... it means that everyone who lives in Uzbekistan and connects his fate with this holy land should live with a sense of responsibility, not "what my country gave me", but "what I am doing for the development of my country" [2] .

It can be seen that the national-mental, theological and axiological traditions, customs, rich spiritual heritage of our society, and the great life experience of our society, lead to the expected results, and avoid various risks. For example, in the East, the role and importance of the family, the enlightened old man and the advice of old mothers, the neighborhood, and finally the community have been great. The development of professional skills and competences of entrepreneurs, serving them to fully understand the legislation related to the field, and eliminating disputes, disagreements and conflicts that threaten social stability, can be solved only by forming a system of respecting its moral image, as well as the rights of others along with one's own rights. In the implementation of the above-mentioned system, the peace and prosperity of legal cultured persons will be determined by inviting them to be active in public life. As a result, entrepreneurs with legal culture also increase their activity in the improvement of their surroundings, place of residence, and our society as a whole. It follows that these experienced individuals who participated in the management of the country were progressive thinkers of their time, that is, people who deserve to be called creators of their time.

Entrepreneurship, creativity and generally innovative qualities of an entrepreneur are the qualities that guarantee the socio-economic development of our society. In the history of the formation of our national statehood, creativity and entrepreneurship in managing the country and society were supported by the public. Also, all people should have an internal protection system that protects them from negative diseases. This defense system is usually called immunity, that is, moral immunity. Positive qualities such as strong faith, honor, firm faith are established in the psyche of a person with such protection, and he is protected from spiritual dangers. It is effective for a person to constantly look at his work in the spirit of criticism in order to strengthen this defense system. As an important element in the protection system - family environment and upbringing, as well as it will be necessary to translate our religious values into a separate language. The family institution of our society has developed its own immune system under the influence of spiritual values, interpersonal relationships between parents and children. In this, the formation

of standards between positive qualities and negative vices, the ability of people to make correct conclusions in their actions and apply them in practice with positive views, by inculcating theological views in an inclusive form, independent thinking, striving to avoid mistakes in personal relationships, not to harm others through their activities, legal actions, socially oriented patronage is encouraged. Based on this, as a result of the integration of the passive and active actions of the individual, an attempt was made to study the specific aspects of the areas of entrepreneurial activity as a special branch.

The internal experiences of a person have the characteristics of both horizontal and vertical evolutionary development, which, as noted above, develops through education, life experience, rational conclusions, and the correct implementation of these relationships leads to creativity, activity, hard work, patriotism, business, entrepreneurship, creativity and in general. , calls for physical and intellectual innovation. As a result of orderly activity, a person is able to fulfill two tasks before him: first, if he achieves order of his inner world through his social activity and efficiency. Secondly, he wants not only spiritual, but also material incentive for his work, which in the end - gives rise to a sense of ownership. Before our independence, we have observed that the activity of the second direction by the individual was limited, and the collective interest prevailed over the individual interest.

When a person produces material goods, he rightfully wants to be interested in it, to benefit from it, to live peacefully with his family on the basis of material interest, and to not stifle his will and initiatives. We know well from historical examples and memories from the recent past that prohibition, repression, and bureaucratic barriers are a great barrier to free activity. It follows from this that an entrepreneur, imbued with oriental values, should be distinguished in his activities not only by his own interests, but also by social aspects, i.e., by creative work such as benefiting the society and leaving a good garden.

However, the role of traditions and values, education and upbringing with a view to the future is extremely important in the social importance of creativity, in leaving a significant mark in the life of the country and nation. For example, young people's confidence in the future is not created by itself. At the heart of this lies concrete work aimed at the path of national happiness - ideological education. Therefore, ideological education should become a clear, scientifically based program for achieving awareness, creativity, and creativity. It includes the

formation of a personal attitude to the domestic and foreign policy of our country at every age through propaganda that has new content and meaning.

In the current conditions, it is of great importance to protect the position of Uzbekistan as a region free from any dangers, to make our motherland more free and prosperous. It turns out that entrepreneurship and creativity are twin concepts. As we mentioned above, the nature of entrepreneurship has been formed by living a conscious life of mankind. In the early clan-tribal system, it required perseverance and thinking from its members to manage it, which created the initial business environment, and made a big turn compared to the production of the time they lived. Those who surprised people with their discoveries. For example, our great scholar Alisher Navoi, heroes like Farhad mentioned in his "Khamsa" are not only people's favorite symbols, but it is no exaggeration to say that they were businessmen (entrepreneurs) of their time.

In essence, an entrepreneur does not open a path only for himself by developing his business. As his work on a legal basis, under the protection of the law, gives great results, the contribution of these results to the development of the society naturally increases. Thus, the embodiment of national and universal values in an entrepreneur is evaluated as a positive quality in their activity. Such practical results have been observed in countries with high economic indicators of the world, in particular, Singapore, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and at the same time India, China and other countries that have chosen the path of great development.

One of the achievements of the years of independence has been the emergence, albeit slowly, of a propertied class. The class of entrepreneurs or owners has a place in the development of our country and is gaining great importance. "Accordingly speaking, now practitioners and entrepreneurs have become the leading stratum of our society - writes the famous mystic scientist Professor Najmiddin Komilov, - Among them there are those who know several foreign languages, have gained experience by traveling around the world, participate in international trade, bankers, and businessmen. They are new thinkers. Frankly, there are not among them those who are fond of the western way of life, and there are also extreme "practitioners" who think only about increasing money day and night. However, the happy thing is that most of our businessmen and entrepreneurs are loyal to our ancient traditions and religion, they care for Uzbekistan with all their being. I want to increase the number of our owners, who will be recognized by the world and become rich on the basis of our national spirituality, and who will be an example to many people with their personal qualities. After all, a person who has not forgotten his humanity,

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his original lineage, can preserve his identity in any situation, he will be honorable" [3].

To sum up, the great changes that take place in society are usually manifested in the way old principles give way to new ones, that is, in the weakening of the influence of the old ideology on the next generations and its reformation by the new ideology. Therefore, it is not wrong to say that every person's activity embodies the night, day and tomorrow of national creativity. The whole point is that not all people strive to bring out this "embodied feeling" in the heart. The level of personal activity and legal culture plays a decisive role here.

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